

TEACHING CULTURE TO YOUNG LEARNERS THROUGH STORYTELLING

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Annotation: Teaching English to young learners is not an easy task. It differs from teaching teens or adults. The minds' of young learners are in the process of learning the world. So, to think that teaching those little kids is an easy task is nonsense. Sharing stories is an exciting and entertaining way to engage learners and present new language structures and vocabulary. Providing a meaningful context in which the target language is used and taught is important. Storytelling allows students to communicate in the language authentically and introduces them to their own culture and other cultures. Narrative activities develop learners' critical thinking, listening, and speaking skills, and can be integrated with follow-up activities for teaching reading and writing.

Keywords: storytelling, young learners, teaching English, critical thinking skills, communication.

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Аннотация: Обучение английскому языку маленьких учеников - непростая задача. Это отличается от обучения подростков или взрослых. Умы маленьких учеников находятся в процессе познания мира. Поэтому думать, что обучать этих маленьких детей - легкая задача, бессмысленно. Обмен историями - это увлекательный и занимательный способ вовлечь учащихся и познакомить их с новыми языковыми структурами и словарным запасом. Важно создать содержательный контекст, в котором используется и преподается изучаемый язык. Рассказывание историй позволяет учащимся общаться на родном языке и знакомит их со своей собственной и другими культурами. Повествовательная деятельность развивает у учащихся навыки критического мышления, аудирования и устной речи и может быть интегрирована с последующими занятиями по обучению чтению и письму.

Ключевые слова: рассказывание историй, молодые учащиеся, преподавание английского языка, навыки критического мышления, коммуникация.

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Annotatsiya: Yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini o'rgatish oson ish emas. Bu o'smirlar yoki kattalarni o'qitishdan farq qiladi. Yosh o'quvchilarning ongi dunyoni o'rganish jarayonida. Shunday qilib, bu kichik bolalarni o'rgatish oson ish deb o'ylash to'g'ri emas. Hikoyalardan foydalanish- o'quvchilarni jalb qilish, yangi til tuzilmalari va so'z boyligini taqdim etishning qiziqarli va mazmunli usulidir. Maqsadli tildan foydalaniladigan va o'qitiladigan mazmunli kontekstni ta'minlash muhimdir. Hikoyalar talabalarga tilda haqiqiy muloqot qilish imkonini beradi va ularni o'z madaniyati va boshqa xalqlar madaniyatlari bilan tanishtiradi. Hikoya faoliyati o'quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash, tinglash va nutq qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi hamda o'qish va yozishni o'rgatish bo'yicha qo'shimcha mashqlar bilan bilan uyg'unlashtirilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: hikoya qilish, yosh o'quvchilar, ingliz tilini o'rgatish, tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlari, muloqot.

Introduction

In many cultures, storytelling is a tradition used to communicate culture from generation to generation. Children are actively involved with the storyteller and genuinely enjoy this traditional communication between generations.

As Pinter describes, "listening to stories is the most authentic and popular activity for all children, and Primary English teachers can use storytelling as additional listening practice. Children will learn a new language as well as have enjoyable listening practice. Language is picked up easily because stories contain repetition, making linguistic input more noticeable". Storytelling is considered to be most beneficial for young learners of English for some reasons:

It is an authentic form of communication. Additionally, it introduces new cultures to the children and entertainingly teaches young learners. It helps develop critical thinking skills.

According to Halima Saidahmedovna (2024), incorporating storytelling into English language teaching profoundly benefits young learners' proficiency development. Stories ignite the passion for learning English, accelerate vocabulary

acquisition, improve listening and reading fluency, spur productive language use, hone comprehension abilities, and expand cultural awareness. Teachers should leverage children's innate love of imaginative tales to make language learning creative, impactful, and fun. With the magic of stories, the English journey of young minds will be both pleasurable and fruitful.

Additionally, well-chosen stories stimulate student engagement and interest-key ingredients for effective language uptake. The enchanting worlds, curious characters, and suspenseful plots spark children's wonder. This curiosity hooks them into learning by forging an emotional connection and desire to keep listening or reading to uncover more. Their imagination is lit up as they visualize scenes or empathize with the protagonists. This engagement results in higher motivation, attention, and time spent immersed in English.

Stories can also be used to bring a student's attention to their everyday life by tackling topics relevant to the growing child's everyday life experience (Khaleel, 2017). While simple stories with straightforward moral and ethical endings may be acceptable for a very young child, for the growing teen it is crucial to engage them in a higher and more critical level of thinking skills. According to Cambridge University, storytelling is integral to human identity, both culturally and personally. It's a natural inclination for children, manifesting in various forms and situations. However, storytelling's relevance isn't confined to young learners; teenagers and adults can also derive value from it in educational settings. Stories and the art of storytelling precede written language, tapping into an inherent aspect of the human psyche. Even if one doesn't see oneself as a proficient storyteller, daily recounting experiences or dreams involves storytelling. This innate ability to craft narratives extends to sharing odd or nonsensical dreams with friends.

Materials and methods

As Pinter describes, "listening to stories is the most authentic and popular activity for all children, and Primary English teachers can use storytelling as additional listening practice. Children will learn a new language as well as have enjoyable listening practice. Language is picked up easily because stories contain repetition, making linguistic input more noticeable" (2006, pp. 52-53).

Throughout human history, stories have been a fundamental tool for conveying knowledge, dating back to the earliest forms of communication. Despite this, educators may not have fully recognized the potential of storytelling as a teaching method. This comprehensive review aimed at educators explores the relationship between teaching and storytelling. Scientists discuss various storytelling techniques, elucidate why storytelling is effective in education, and offer practical suggestions for incorporating storytelling into teaching practices. While acknowledging potential drawbacks and

limitations, they urge psychology educators to embrace storytelling as a valuable pedagogical strategy to engage students and achieve desired learning objectives.

According to Enever (2006), since the early 1990s, teaching English as a foreign language to young learners (TEYL) has experienced an expansion of provision. In agreement, Pinter (2006) describes that nowadays, all around the world children are learning more and more English as a foreign language or a second language in different contexts. There is a constant debate about acquiring a second language at a young age. Some experts like Singleton & Cook (2014) agree that age is an important factor to consider and add that the effects of starting at an early age are consistently positive. Another expert Carmen Muñoz (2014) summarizes that very young learners could experience input limitations and as a result, they do not have long-term advantages in second language acquisition. Despite this fact, age is not a predictor of second language acquisition, and everything depends on the amount of comprehensible input and the level of the affective filter (Krashen, 1982). Karen Lichtman (2018) defines input as “the language that learners see or hear in a communicative (meaning-bearing) context” (p.1) and explains why it needs to be comprehensible. According to her, comprehensible input is “the language that a learner can, in general, understand; language whose basic message is comprehensible by the learner.” (p.4).⁶ With these concepts in mind, new research has started to go further and investigate how comprehensible input can be included in teaching English as a second language to young learners. In 2018 there was news about information collected regarding comprehensible input and young learners. A methodology called TPRS (Teaching Proficiency through Reading and Storytelling) created by Blaine Ray in 1990 has been studied since it came out by some researchers to understand the relation between comprehensible input and the methodology. They wanted to see if TPRS could be applied to very young learners, even though it was created to be used for secondary students, but very few conclusions have yet been reached. Hence, to grasp and promote understandable input in English as a second language class for young learners, teachers must discern the methodologies that prove effectiveness. TPRS could be an interesting methodology to introduce comprehensible input as much as possible for young learners although not enough studies have yet been done.

Why does Storytelling work? Many of the tools for understanding why storytelling works come from our discipline of psychology. Finkel (2000) argues that storytelling is highly effective in education due to its concrete, specific, and narrative nature. When teachers adopt a storytelling approach, they can present material as a mystery, prompting students to engage in sense-making as they unravel the narrative. Willingham (2009) describes stories as “psychologically privileged,” suggesting that memory for stories differs from memory for other types of information. Essentially, remembering is not solely reliant on having a good or bad memory; even individuals

with "bad" memories can recall memorable stories. This is because stories are woven with a plot, hold personal meaning, evoke vivid imagery, or elicit strong emotions that are more likely to be remembered. Moreover, a good story leaves a lasting impression by creating a meaningful and emotionally stimulating narrative. Surprisingly, the more specific the story, the more universally it resonates.

Ruscher (2014) emphasizes a three-part storytelling approach—meaningfulness, coherence, and memorability—particularly when communicating psychological concepts to students or the public. Fortunately, psychology offers a wealth of personally relevant topics, making it easier to connect with audiences. Cognitive science further supports the effectiveness of storytelling by revealing that human brains are naturally inclined to process experiences sequentially, akin to the structure of a narrative. Like stories, memories are constructed, with certain features highlighted and elements of fiction incorporated to maintain narrative coherence. Other aspects of cognition also facilitate our understanding of stories. Intersubjectivity allows us to understand and empathize with characters and to fill in the unwritten gaps about their perspectives. We engage in active comprehension as we fill in detail and update our representation model of the story's context in memory, as well as imagine possible worlds through the capacity for hypothetical thinking (for reviews of the cognitive underpinnings of story comprehension, see Copeland, Larson, & Palena, 2015; Foy, 2015).

At an even more basic level, neuroscience researchers suggest that our brains respond to what is happening in a story as if it were a genuine experience. Multiple research studies have discovered that our brains react to viewing or even reading stories much like they do to real life (AbdulSabur et al., 2014; Baldassano, Hasson, & Norman, 2018; Berns, Blaine, Prietula, & Pye, 2013; Milivojevic, Va-radinov, Vicente Grabovetsky, Collin, &Doeller, 2016). Our limbic system, mirror neurons, neurotransmitters, and cortical pathways are all engaged. Our experience of narrative transportation is tangible; as far as many areas of our brains are concerned, we need to enter that other world of the story.

Conclusion

No educational method is a cure-all, as noted by (2006) and Foy (2015), who wisely highlight the potential drawbacks of storytelling in college classrooms. Over-reliance on storytelling may lead students to believe that psychology is solely based on anecdotal evidence rather than empirical research. Additionally, if stories are perceived as mere entertainment or a diversion from course content, they may not serve their intended educational purpose. There's also a risk that students may become overly fixated on specific topics presented in stories and overlook broader themes within psychology.

Despite these concerns, instructors can mitigate these risks by guiding students to focus on the educational aspects of storytelling and ensuring that it enhances, rather than detracts from, the learning experience. While it's important not to exaggerate the significance of storytelling in teaching, it can be a valuable tool when used appropriately. Throughout this review, the primary benefit of storytelling has been emphasized: its ability to enhance memorability and foster emotional engagement through narrative structure. Stories facilitate mutual understanding between individuals, whether a parent sharing a tale with a child or an instructor engaging students in class.

Just as families share stories during gatherings, teachers of psychology exchange narratives at conferences, underscoring the binding nature of storytelling. When used thoughtfully and appropriately, storytelling can serve as a powerful educational method, enhancing the overall learning experience. Therefore, we encourage educators to explore the diverse applications of storytelling in teaching. Moreover, by sharing their experiences and outcomes through scholarly endeavors, teachers can collectively harness the pedagogical power of storytelling to support student learning effectively.

To sum up, storytelling undeniably has multifaceted benefits ranging from igniting intrinsic motivation to boosting interpretation skills to providing springboards for creative linguistic expression. Stories help convert language instruction from dry grammar practice into enjoyable journeys of the imagination. Leading children through stories from diverse cultures not only enhances their English language skills but also expands their worldview. By integrating frequent and diverse storytelling sessions, educators can ignite a sense of joy and make language learning more impactful. Through captivating narratives, classrooms evolve into environments where students can develop linguistic proficiency, creativity, and cultural awareness, thus nurturing globally-minded citizens. It's time for schools worldwide to acknowledge the immense potential of storytelling in achieving success in English language teaching.

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